

TABLE 2
B/l.mol⁻¹

Temp. °C	Weight % of					
	Dioxane		Glycol		Methanol	
	10	20	30	10	20	30
Sr(NO ₃) ₂						
30	0.265	0.270	0.500	0.355	0.390	0.530
35	0.270	0.380	0.555	0.360	0.480	0.550
40	0.280	0.430	0.605	0.420	0.500	0.620
45	0.290	0.480	0.680	0.520	0.610	0.695
Cd(NO ₃) ₂						
30	0.170	0.340	0.450	0.305	0.420	0.500
35	0.195	0.410	0.485	0.390	0.520	0.610
40	0.250	0.475	0.530	0.390	0.540	0.660
45	0.315	0.545	0.580	0.420	0.590	0.710

Dependence of 'B' on temperature : According to Stokes and Mills⁶, the viscosity of dilute electrolytic solutions incorporates that of the solvent and the contribution from other sources. They are η^E , the positive increase due to the shape and size of the ion, η^A , the increase due to the alignment or orientation of the polar molecules by the ionic field and η^D , the decrease in viscosity arising out of the distortion of the solvent structure. Therefore 'B' coefficients can be discussed in terms of these viscosity effects at different temperatures.

The 'B' coefficients of both the salts increase with increase in temperature. This indicates that the viscosity decrease due to the solvent structure η^D is small and $\eta^E + \eta^A > \eta^D$ and 'B' is positive. The 'B' value is found to be of the order Sr²⁺ > Cd²⁺ and glycol+water > dioxane+water > methyl alcohol+water in case of both the salts. The lesser the value of 'B', the greater is the ion-solvent interaction. So the ion-solvent interaction is of the order Cd²⁺ > Sr²⁺.

According to Stokes and Mills⁶, the lesser the value of $\frac{dB}{dt}$ the greater is the ion solvent interaction. In the present case, the plot of B vs t is linear and the slope $\frac{dB}{dt}$ is found to be of the order glycol+water > dioxane+water > methyl alcohol+water. So the ion solvent interaction is of the reverse order methyl alcohol+water > dioxane+water > glycol+water.

Dioxane is more basic and less acidic than water because of the electron releasing tendency of the methylene group in the molecule. Water molecules which are hydrogen bonded with oxygen atoms of dioxane molecules become more basic and less acidic than pure water. A cation will interact more strongly with the oxygen atoms of dioxane+water mixtures and an anion will react more strongly with hydrogen atoms. This type of ion-solvent interaction is in the primary solvation sheath.

The addition of small amounts of dioxane may give rise to two effects. If the dioxane is accommodated in the solvent structure, it may strengthen the

water structure because dioxane is a better proton acceptor. If it cannot be accommodated because of its bulky size, it may cause a breakdown in the three dimensional water structure. The 'B' value appears to be less than that of glycol+water mixtures. This indicates that dioxane is not accommodated in the solvent structure and hence it breaks down the three dimensional water structure.

Glycol has two -OH groups and methyl alcohol has one -OH group, whereas water is both an electron donor and acceptor. Methyl alcohol accepts a proton and hence the three dimensional water structure is easily broken. Glycol, though containing two -OH groups, is not able to break the hydrogen bond of water so easily as the -CH₂OH groups are linked with each other. So the ion-solvent interaction order is MeOH+water > dioxane+water > glycol+water.

References

1. P. B. DAS, *Electrochim. Acta*, 1981, **26**, 1099.
2. P. P. MISRA and P. B. DAS, *Electrochim. Acta*, 1978, **23**, 1233.
3. N. C. DAS and P. B. DAS, *Electrochim. Acta*, 1980, **25**, 725.
4. P. B. DAS, *J. Instn. of Chem.*, 1970, **42**, 70.
5. G. JONES and M. DOLÉ, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, **51**, 2950.
6. R. H. STOKES and R. MILLS, "The International Encyclopedia of Physical Chemistry and Chemical Physics", Pergamon Press, New York, 1965, Vol. 3.

Microdetermination of Quinone and Hydroquinone by Differential Pulse Polarography

D. AMIN and F. M. EL-SAMMAN

Department of Chemistry, College of Science,
University of Mosul, Mosul, Iraq

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MANY polarographic methods have been proposed in literature for the determination of quinone¹⁻³ and hydroquinone^{4,5}. The polarography of quinones⁶ and polarographic application of hydroquinone as a reductimetric reagent⁷ have been reviewed. Determination of quinone by reduction with iodide, and determination of hydroquinone by oxidation with iodine, have been recommended⁸. However, some of these methods are not sensitive, while others are time consuming or require a large sample for analysis.

In an attempt to develop a sensitive and accurate method for the determination of quinone and hydroquinone, we have investigated the application of differential pulse polarography. The present paper describes a method based on the reduction of the

acidic sample solution of quinone by iodide, extraction of the liberated iodine into chloroform followed by its reduction with sodium hydrogen sulphite⁹ to iodide, and oxidation of the resulting iodide with bromine water to iodate, which is measured polarographically.

Alternatively, hydroquinone is oxidized with a chloroform solution of iodine, whose excess is removed, followed by polarographic determination of the iodate formed, after bromine oxidation of the iodide.

The present paper investigates the applicability of differential pulse polarography (DPP) for these determinations via quantitative trace determination of iodate ion¹⁰.

Experimental

Apparatus :

A Metrohm E506 Polarecord, with a three-electrode system was used, the working electrode was a dropping mercury electrode (DME), the reference electrode was Ag/AgCl, KCl and the counter electrode was platinum wire. All measurements were performed at 25°. The solutions were deaerated by passing through it a slow stream of pure nitrogen gas for 10 min. The DPP was made with a 100 mV pulse, a 2s drop time and 2 mV s⁻¹ scan rate. All pH measurements were made with a Sargent Model NX pH-meter.

Reagents and Solutions :

All chemicals used were of A. R. grade quality. The solutions were made in distilled water.

Solutions of quinone (concentrations 1.0 and 0.1 mg/ml) in ethanol were prepared and were diluted with ethanol as needed. The solutions were standardized iodometrically⁹. Aqueous solutions of hydroquinone (concentrations 1.0 and 0.1 mg/ml) were prepared in 1 N sulphuric acid. Dilutions were carried out in acid medium. The solutions were standardized against ceric sulphate solution¹¹. Iodine solution was prepared weekly by dissolving about 0.3 g of pure iodine in 250 ml of pure dry chloroform. Standard solutions of potassium iodate were made by dissolving accurately weighed amounts. The modified universal Britton-Robinson buffer was used as supporting electrolyte and prepared as given by Britton¹².

Oxygen-free nitrogen gas was obtained by passing the stream of gas through a purification train consisting of a bubbler containing pyrogallol followed by another bubbler containing 1 N HCl and an empty one.

Procedure :

Quinone :

In a 50 ml separating funnel, a suitable volume of sample solution containing 2-1000 µg of quinone and 5 ml of 4 N hydrochloric acid are introduced followed by 2.5 ml of potassium iodide solution

(5 mg I⁻). Water is added to make a total aqueous phase volume of 15 ml. The liberated iodine is extracted with two 10 ml portions of chloroform. The extracts are collected in another funnel and the iodine solution is shaken with 10 ml water containing 0.5 ml of 0.5% sodium hydrogen sulphite solution to reduce the iodine to iodide. The aqueous layer is transferred to a 50 ml calibrated flask, 3 ml of bromine water is added and the mixture shaken for 3 min. The excess of bromine is destroyed with 0.5 ml formic acid, 0.5 ml of gelatin solution and 10 ml of Britton-Robinson buffer are added and the pH of the solution is adjusted to 9.3 by the addition of about 4.5 ml of 4 N sodium hydroxide solution. The volume is made up to the mark with water. A portion of the sample solution is transferred to the polarographic vessel, deaerated with a stream of nitrogen gas for 10 min and the iodate wave starting at -0.8V vs Ag/AgCl electrode is recorded. A blank is run and the heights of each of the blank and sample waves are compared with the calibration graph to obtain the amount of iodate equivalent to quinone and the amount of quinone is calculated.

Hydroquinone :

In a 50 ml separating funnel, a suitable volume of sample solution containing 3-1000 µg of hydroquinone, 0.5 ml 4 N acetic acid, 5 ml 2 N sodium acetate are taken and water is added to make a total aqueous phase volume of 15 ml. 5 ml of iodine solution is added and the mixture allowed to stand for 5 min. The organic layer is separated and the remaining iodine in the aqueous phase is extracted with two 10 ml portions of chloroform. The aqueous phase (containing iodide) is drained into a 50 ml calibrated flask, and treated in the manner described for quinone. A blank determination is run and the amount of equivalent hydroquinone is calculated.

Calibration graph :

To a series of 50 ml calibrated flasks, suitable volumes of standard potassium iodate solutions containing 0.1-150 ppm iodate are introduced. 3 ml of saturated bromine water, 0.5 ml of formic acid, 0.5 ml of gelatin solution, 10 ml of Britton-Robinson buffer solution are added and the pH of the solution is adjusted to 9.3 by adding about 4.5 ml of 4 N sodium hydroxide solution. The solutions are diluted to the mark with water. The polarographic iodate wave for each sample starting at -0.8V vs Ag/AgCl electrode is measured. A reagent blank is prepared similarly. Response of height pulse peak as a function of concentration of iodate is linear, passing through the origin.

Results and Discussion

A strong acid solution of quinone is quantitatively reduced to hydroquinone by iodide and liberates an equivalent amount of iodine⁹. Preliminary studies showed that the reaction between quinone and excess of iodide is rapid and should not be allowed to continue for more than 1 min, due

to the air oxidation of iodide, which gives high results. 5 mg of iodide covers the range of quinone determined in the present work.

Under suitable conditions, hydroquinone can be quantitatively oxidized to quinone by iodine⁸. The small amount of acetic acid (optimum 0.1-0.5 ml of 4 N acetic acid) must be added before the addition of acetate (optimum 5 ml of 2 N sodium acetate) to prevent the aerial oxidation of some of hydroquinone in alkaline solution. It was found that 5 ml of 0.12% iodine solution is essential for rapid and quantitative oxidation of up to 1 mg of hydroquinone. Any iodine left in the aqueous phase would cause high results and hence must be removed by washing the aqueous phase with chloroform.

The iodate waves were best recorded at pH 9.3¹⁰ with a half wave potential ($E_{1/2}$) of -1.24 V. The blank runs gave iodate waves of 0.6 and 0.9 cm height using a sensitivity of 2.5×10^{-6} A/mm.

The working procedures finally developed were applied to the analysis of solutions as dilute as 1.2×10^{-6} M quinone and 1.8×10^{-6} M hydroquinone. The accuracy and precision (3 replicates) of the method were checked. Results given in Table 1 indicate the reliability of the method.

TABLE 1—MICRODETERMINATION OF QUINONE AND HYDROQUINONE BY DIFFERENTIAL PULSE POLAROGRAPHY

Quinone Taken	Quinone Found*	Relative error %	SD %	Hydroquinone Taken	Hydroquinone Found*	Relative error %	SD %
2	1.9	-5.0	5.3	3	2.9	-3.3	3.9
5	4.9	-2.0	3.8	5	4.9	-2.0	3.2
10	10.1	+1.0	1.2	10	9.9	-1.0	1.6
100	99.9	-0.1	0.2	100	100.5	+0.5	0.3
1000	996.8	-0.3	0.5	1000	997.8	-0.2	0.4

* Mean of 3 determinations.

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References

1. S. N. SUSLOV and D. I. STOM, *Zh. Anal. Khim.*, 1978, 33, 1423.
2. Y. A. GAWARGIOUS and S. W. BISHARA, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1969, 245, 366.
3. T. A. SMIRNOVA, YU. P. BRYVIN and B. P. YATSENKO, *Proizvod. Khim. Prom-sti.*, 1977, 4, 44; *Anal. Abs.*, 1979, 36, 3085.
4. V. D. BEZUGLYL and V. N. DMITRIEVA, *Zavodskaya Lab.*, 1958, 24, 941; *Chem. Abs.*, 1960, 54, 11539i.
5. J. W. HAMILTON and A. L. TAPPEL, *J. Amer. Oil Chemist's Soc.*, 1963, 40, 52; *Chem. Abs.*, 1963, 58, 10498f.
6. H. BERG and K. KRAMARCZYK, *Talanta*, 1965, 12, 1127.
7. A. BERKA, J. VULTERIN and J. ZVKA, *Chemist Analyst*, 1962, 51, 88.
8. I. M. KOLTHOFF and R. BELCHER, "Volumetric Analysis", Interscience, New York, 1957, Vol. 3, p. 396.

9. W. GEILMANN and H. BARTLINGEK, *Mikrochemie*, 1942, 30, 217.
10. Y. M. TEMERK, M. E. AHMED and M. M. KAMAL, *Zh. Anal. Khim.*, 1980, 301, 414.
11. G. G. RAO and T. P. SASTRI, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1958, 163, 263.
12. H. T. S. BRITTON, "Hydrogen Ions", 2nd Edn., Chapman and Hall, London, 1952, Vol. 1, p. 362.

Synthesis of New Quinazolin-4-One Derivatives as Possible Antifertility/Anthelmintic Agents

Y. D. KULKARNI*, S. H. R. ABDI

and

B. KUMAR

Department of Chemistry, University of Lucknow, Lucknow-226 007

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SIGNIFICANT anti-implantation activity among triphenyl ethylene moiety in a rigid frame-work having methoxy groups and/or basic amine residues as in dihydronaphthalene^{1,2}, chromans^{3,4}, indoles^{5,6}, benzofurans⁷, quinazolones⁸ provided the necessary lead for the syntheses of 2-phenyl-3-(3'-aminomethyl-4-hydroxyphenyl)-quinazolinones (III) and 2-phenyl/3,4,5-trimethoxy phenyl-3-(2'-methoxy/3,4,5'-trimethoxy phenyl)-6-substituted quinazolin-4-ones (IV) as possible antifertility agents.

Further, high anthelmintic activity exhibited by substituted quinazolones⁹⁻¹² tempted the authors to screen these compounds for this activity as well.

4-Aminophenol and 2-phenyl benzoxazine (I) were condensed at 170-80° to yield 2-phenyl-3-(4'-hydroxyphenyl)-quinazolin-4-one (II) which was subjected to Mannich reaction to yield III (Scheme 1). Six benzoxazines (I₁₋₆) were condensed with aromatic amines to yield IV (Scheme 1).

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillary and are uncorrected. Reactions were followed by tlc. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer and nmr spectra were run on a Varian A-60D instrument using TMS as the internal standard.

6-Substituted-2-aryl benzoxazine-2-ones (Table 1; I₁₋₆) were prepared according to published procedure^{1,3}.

2-Phenyl-3-(4'-hydroxyphenyl)-quinazolin-4-one (II): 2-Phenyl-benzoxazine-4-one (I₁, 2.23 g; 0.01 mole) and 4-aminophenol (1.1 g; 0.01 mole) were heated on an oil bath at 160-80° for 1/2 hr. The residue was crystallized from aqueous ethanol,